

A STUDY ON ORGANISATIONAL CLIMATE OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS AS PERCEIVED BY TEACHERS

Mr. John Mohammad¹ & Dr. Yashpal D. Netragaonkar

Associate Professor, MIT World Peace University, School Of Education,
Kothrud Pune

Paper Received On: 20 MAR 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 28 APRIL 2024

Published On: 01 MAY 2024

Abstract

This research paper is an attempt to study the organizational climate of secondary schools as perceived by teachers. The survey method of descriptive research has been adopted to carry out the study. The study was carried out in Kashmir division of Jammu and Kashmir. Simple random technique was adopted to select a sample of 600 teachers working in govt as well as private secondary school teachers in Kashmir. The findings of the study showed different satisfaction levels with respect to the organisational climate of their respective schools with majority of the teachers moderately satisfied with the organisational climate.

Key Words: Organisational Climate, Secondary School, Teachers, Kashmir.

Introduction: One of the most important elements of every nation's educational system is undoubtedly its teachers. Teachers who want to provide a constructive approach need to be balanced in all areas—physically, psychologically, monetarily, and socially. Teachers encourage children to succeed in life, give them a purpose, and position them for success. In order for the teacher to fulfill the various requirements of the children, a certain amount of autonomy must be granted to them (Panneerselvam & Muthamizhselvan, 2015). Teachers' primary responsibilities include instructing, assessing, communicating, advising, and counseling in addition to planning extracurricular activities, taking part in community service projects, diagnosing and resolving student issues, and more. Effective teaching and having high-quality teachers are important components of teacher education in order to carry out this type of work (Chakraborty, 2017). However, the process of producing excellent teachers can only take place if both teachers and students are afforded the same amount of autonomy and

flexibility. His or her opinions and views must also be heard by his or her colleagues and superiors, as they frequently make decisions that impact the institution's immediate institutional climate (Panneerselvam & Muthamizhselvan, 2015). The core of an institution can be defined by its institutional environment, which can be represented as a personality sketch of the same, just as personality describes a character (Sharma, 1982). If the institutional or work climate is improving, a teacher will demonstrate inventive, creative, and motivating work patterns (Gemnafle, et al., 2016).

The way that people or members of the organization perceive different facets and activities within an organization is known as the organizational climate (Owens, 2004). It is a well-known fact that teacher competency, sensitivity, and motivation play a major role in determining the quality of student accomplishment (Ghosh & Guha, 2016). More importantly, if teachers lack satisfaction and contentment, the holistic approach to teacher education will not be realized. Teachers' behavior is influenced by the culture of the institution (Akhilesh, 2013). Tagiuri (1968) defined organizational climate as having four dimensions: The term "milieu" refers to the social environment in which all members of the institution interact, including the motivation of pupils and the job satisfaction of teachers. (I) Ecology is related to the physical aspects of the institution, such as infrastructure and technology. (II) (III) Social System is the institution's administrative framework; (IV) Culture is the set of values and beliefs held by those who interact with the institution. The improvement of any institution therefore rests heavily on the patterns of communication and interaction among its stakeholders, and openness of organizational climate plays a critical role in this regard. Teachers who are professional, amiable, collaborative, pleasant, and dedicated to teaching pupils, as well as institution directors who are professional, encouraging, and do not impose rules on teachers, define an open atmosphere. Conversely, an environment that is closed off is typified by non-professional educators who lack professionalism and are aloof. Additionally, the head of the institution may be rigid and unsupportive.

Need and Importance of the Study

The quality of a country is directly related to the quality of its schools, and the effectiveness of schools is directly related to the effectiveness of its instructors as well as the interaction of various internal and external influences that affect how successfully the schools accomplish their objectives. The organisational climate and teacher satisfaction in schools have a major role in determining their efficacy and stability.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the Organisational Climate of Secondary Schools as perceived by the teachers.
2. To compare the Organisational climate of Government and Private Secondary Schools as perceived by the teachers.

Hypotheses of the Study:

1. There is no significant difference between Organisational climate of Government and Private Secondary Schools as perceived by the teachers.

Operational definition of the variable:

Organisational climate: The conditions of a school's organisational environment are those that will have an impact on teaching and learning. For the purposes of this study, the organisational climate is defined as the teachers' expressed satisfaction with the principal behaviour, teacher behaviour, student behaviour, and physical amenities.

Delimitation of the study:

1. The study was limited to Kashmir division of Jammu and Kashmir State only.
2. The sample was restricted to 200 secondary school teachers only.
3. The study was limited to investigate the organisational climate with reference to demographic variables like, gender and rural urban dichotomy only.

Research Methodology:

The survey method of descriptive research has been deemed the best way for carrying out the study.

Population:

The population for the present investigation includes all the Government and Private school teachers in Kashmir.

Sample:

Teachers from Government and private schools make up the study's sample. There are 600 teachers in the entire sample for the current study, 300 of whom work in government schools and 300 of whom work in private schools in Kashmir. The sample was selected by using simple random technique of sampling.

Sample distribution

Sample	Variable	Category	Sample Size	Total	Total
Govt. school Teachers	Gender	Male	150	300	600
		Female	150		
Private school Teachers		Male	150	300	
		Female	150		

Tool used for the study:

Organisational Climate Scale:

Organisational climate scale by M. Sridevi was used to measure the organisational atmosphere. The following dimensions of the organisational atmosphere of government schools and private schools were measured using the scale: Principal Behavior, Teacher Behavior, Student Behavior, and D) Dissenting Opinions. Climate, Physical.

Statistical Methods Employed:

Mean, S.D and t-test was used to analyze the data.

Analysis and interpretation:

Table-1showing Organizational Climate of Government and Private Secondary Schools as Perceived by Teachers

S. No	Government School		Private School		Teachers perception of Organisational Climate(Z–Score Range)
	No. of Teachers	Percentage	No. Of Teachers	Percentage	
1	29	9.67%	36	12%	Extremely Satisfied (+1.26to 2.00and above)
2	69	23%	75	25%	Satisfied (+0.51to+1.25)
3	123	41%	98	32.67%	Moderately satisfied (-0.51to+0.50)
4	39	13%	54	18%	Dissatisfied (-0.51to–1.25)
5	40	13.33%	37	12.33%	Extremely dissatisfied (-1.26to-2.00and below)

The organisational atmosphere in Government Schools and Private Schools is depicted, with 9.67% of Government Teachers and 12% of Private Teachers Rating Their Satisfaction As Extremely High, against 23% of Government Teachers and 25% of Private Teachers Rating Their Satisfaction As Satisfied. Additionally, it was found that 41% of teachers in Government schools and 32.67% of teachers in private schools were moderately satisfied, 13% of teachers in Government schools and 18% of teachers in private schools were dissatisfied, and 13.33% of teachers in Government schools and 12.33% of teachers in private schools were extremely dissatisfied.

The table also reveals from the percentage of scores that more number of teachers from both the groups exhibited moderately satisfied Organisational climate. The table also shows almost equal distribution of satisfied and unsatisfied Organisational climate for Government School and Private School.

Table 2: Mean, S.D and t-Values of Organisational Climate and Its Dimensions as Perceived by Whole Sample of Teachers.

S. No	Dimensions	Sample	N	Mean	S.D	't'-Value
1	Organizational climate	GST	300	210.16	11.502	10.17**
		PST	300	197.91	16.245	
2	Principal Behavior	GST	300	51.11	5.964	7.239**
		PST	300	47.88	7.075	
3	Teachers Behavior	GST	300	50.62	4.213	5.580**
		PST	300	51.25	6.380	
4	Student Behavior	GST	300	52.35	4.654	5.737**
		PST	300	51.64	5.099	
5	Physical Climate	GST	300	54.09	5.445	9.283**
		PST	300	52.15	7.012	

a). **Organizational Climate of Government School and Private School with reference to whole Sample of Teachers.**

Table 2 shows the summary of 't' test (10.17) indicating that there is significant difference between the whole sample of Government School and

Private School teachers with reference to their Organisational climate. Thus rejecting the formulated null hypothesis at 0.01 level of significance. The mean score for Government School Organisational climate were higher than those for Private School, which show that Government School teachers felt a better Organisational climate than the Private School teachers.

b). Principal Behavior dimension of Organisational Climate in Government School and Private School with reference to Whole Sample of Teachers.

Table 2 shows the summary of the "t" test (7.23) revealing that the Principal Behavior component of organisational climate significantly differs between the entire sample of teachers from Government Schools and Private Schools. As a result, the null hypothesis was disproved at the significance level of 0.01. Government school instructors performed on average better than private school teachers in the organisational climate's major behavior factor. Therefore, it can be said that instructors at Government Schools experienced the organisational climate's major conduct dimension more favorably than teachers in Private Schools.

c). Teacher Behavior dimension of Organisational Climate in Government School and Private School with reference to whole Sample of Teachers.

Above table presents the summary of the "t" test (5.58) revealing that the Teacher Behavior dimension of Organizational Climate significantly differs between the entire sample of Government School and Private School instructors. As a result, the null hypothesis was disproved at the significance level of 0.01. In the organisational climate's Teacher behaviour dimension, Government School teachers' mean scores were higher than those of Private School teachers. As a result, it can be said that instructors at government schools felt more positively about the organisational climate's teacher behaviour dimension than teachers in private schools.

d). Student Behavior Dimension of Organisational Climate in Government School and Private School with reference to whole Sample of Teachers.

Table shows the summary of the "t" test (5.73) suggesting that there is a significant difference between the entire sample of instructors from government and private schools with regard to the organisational climate's student behavior component. Consequently, the proposed null hypothesis is disproved at the significance level of 0.01. In the organisational climate's Student Behavior dimension, Government School teachers' mean scores were higher than those of Private School educators. Therefore, it can be said that Government School instructors felt more positively about the organisational climate's Student Behavior

dimension than did Private School teachers.

e). Physical Climate dimension of Organisational Climate in Government School and Private School with reference to Whole Sample Of Teachers.

Table presents the summary of the "t" test (9.28), which reveals a significant difference in the organisational climate's physical climate between the entire sample of teachers from government and private schools. As a result, the null hypothesis was disproved at the significance level of 0.01. In the organisational climate's Physical Climate dimension, Government School teachers' mean scores were greater than those of Private School educators. Therefore, it can be said that instructors at Government Schools experienced the Physical Environment dimension of organisational climate better than teachers in Private Schools.

It was found that, Government School had better Organisational climate as a whole and its dimensions than the Private School. It is also observed that in both the Schools, the physical climate dimension of Organisational climate was better than other dimensions of Organisational climate, and the lowest Organisational climate dimension was principal behavior in both the Schools

Conclusions: On the basis of the above findings the following conclusions have been drawn through. The results demonstrate that more instructors from Government and private schools reported a moderately satisfied work environment. Additionally, it demonstrates that instructor satisfaction with various response percentages ranged from extreme discontent to extreme satisfaction. The principal's tendency to act irritably toward the instructors while managing the construction of the school from the ground up, the uncertainty of the position, the uncertainty of the service rules, or the satisfaction of landing a job could all be contributing factors. While curriculum and extracurricular activities are equally important in government schools, student happiness is higher there. In contrast, students at private schools tend to act out more because of the intense academic pressure. Despite what was promised, the infrastructure facilities are great. The findings on Organisational climate of Government school and private school show that teachers felt a better physical climate dimension of Organisational climate and the least satisfaction on principal behavior dimension of Organisational climate Which shows that more thrust is given for physical climate establishment rather than on the selection of a right leader of a school.

References:

Akhilesh, A. (2013). *A comparative study of institutional climate of aided and self- financed teacher education institutions, Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 2(7), pp.41- 46.*

- Chakraborty, T. (2017). *Impact of organisational climate on effectiveness in teaching of secondary educational institutions.*The University of Burdwan, West Bengal, India.
- 140 INDIAN JOURNAL OF LANDSCAPE SYSTEMS AND ECOLOGICAL STUDIES VOL. 43
- Ghosh, M., & Guha, A. (2016). *Organizational climate of teacher education institutions in West Bengal in relation to teacher educators' motivation to work.* IRA International Journal of Education and Multidisciplinary Studies (ISSN 2455–2526), 4(1). doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.21013/jems.v4.n1.p15>.
- Owens, R.G. (2004). *Organizational behavior in education.* New York: Pearson.
- Panneerselvam, M. & Muthamizhselvan, M. (2015). *Study on teaching competence and organisational climate of secondary school teachers.* IJARIE, 1(4), pp. 705-710.
- NO.1 ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE OF TEACHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS 141
- Tagiuri, R. (1968). *Organizational climate: explorations of a concept.* Boston: Division of Research, Graduate School of Business Administration, Harvard University.
- Sharma, M. (1982). *Diagnosing school climate, Naya Bas: International Consultants.*